

D4.2 - Notes on research support and administration from the UCPH Open Days

SYSAGE - Building Excellence in Systems Immunology and Healthy Ageing research

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SYSAGE

Building excellence in Systems Immunology and Healthy Ageing research

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This document contains notes taken at the UCPH Open Days. The notes cover topics such as ERC, MSCA, research data management; IPR and business model issues in relation to Horizon Europe, etc.

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Abbreviations

Acronym	Meaning
AdG	Advanced Grant
AI	Artificial intelligence
CA	Consortium Agreement
CFS	Certificate on the Financial Statements
CoG	Consolidator Grant
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EC	European Commission
ERC	European Research Council
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable principle
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020
HE	Horizon Europe
IA	Innovation Action
IP	Intellectual Property
IRP	Intellectual Property Rights
MSCA	Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions
MSCA-PF	Marie Skłodowska-Curie Postdoctoral Fellowships
OA	Open Access
OLAF	European Anti-Fraud Office
PF	Postdoctoral Fellowships
PI	Principal Investigator
PM	Project Manager
PO	Project Officer
PoC	Proof of Concept Grant
RDM	Research Data Management
RIA	Research and innovation action
SRS	Social Readiness Scale
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities

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STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics
StG	Starting Grant
SyG	Synergy Grant
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UCPH	University of Copenhagen
UTARTU	University of Tartu
WP	Work Package

Table of Contents

Executive Summary.....	6
Introduction and overview of Research support at UCPH	7
Research Data Management.....	8
KU Leuven presentation: proposal peaks	9
Supporting ERC proposals at Norre campus	9
ERC workshop at Helsinki University	11
Supporting MSCA-PF proposals	11
MSCA-PF support at other universities	12
Post-award.....	13
Audits	14
IPR and business models	15
SSH in HE	16
AI.....	16

Executive Summary

This deliverable consists of notes taken during the UCPH Open Days (19–21 May, 2025), attended by Victoriia Biliaieva a representative from UTARTU's grant office. The event focused on research support structures, proposal development, and post-award management within Horizon Europe and other ECR funding schemes.

Introduction and overview of Research support at UCPH

- More than 10,000 employees, around 5,400 scientists, 6 faculties – very different in size.
- About 40% of the funding comes from external grants. Funding from private foundations is growing (e.g. Novo Nordisk), but they only support certain areas. EU funding has become very important. UCPH is very good at ERCs and MSCA.
- UCPH has recently undergone a major research support reform – **from a decentralized to centralized model**. The reform took about 2-3 years. The drive was to provide the same level of support across the whole university; also, to save costs. Now there are 3 administrative centers which support specific departments and institutes. Administrative units within these centers – finance, education, communication, IT, Innovation, HR, research support buildings.
- Research support has pre- and post-award teams. Pre-award team consists of excellence (ERC, MSCA...) and strategic research (Horizon Pillar II and III...).
- Work in Pillar II – demystify complexities, identify researchers who could apply. Recommend to first participate as partners.
- **Support for proposal coordinators:**
 - 5 meetings (1st to scope out and see if there are any red flags for applying).
 - Consultation hours – every week 1 hour for phone calls.
 - Consultations by main/phone – 1-2 day response time.
 - Collecting part A forms, compiling budgets from all partners.
 - Review of proposals – feedback on strengths and weaknesses.
 - EUopSTART scheme – researchers who coordinate can receive monetary support to help with proposals (organize consortium meetings, pay for consultants, graphics etc.).
 - Pre-evaluation – monetary support to bring in experienced EU reviewers to look at almost ready proposals (generalist review – a service from a specific provider; researchers can find specialists).
- Each proposal is unique, often doctoral networks grow into pillar II.
- Challenges and opportunities in relation to the reform:
 - Staff with very different backgrounds, steep learning curve, centralization may lead to compartmentalization.
 - Allows for knowledge sharing and planning during peak times.
 - Pre-award team has multiple stakeholders and needs synergies with other teams.

- There is a need for more deliberate communication with researchers to engage coordinators early on. Present pre-published WPs, go to institutes and present calls.
- If researchers come late, then the pre-award team provides only some services.
- At Helsinki University, there is a pool of approximately 20 project managers, some are funded from projects and some have permanent contracts; there is bridging money available if there is no project for a specific person. At UCPH, 3 PMs per year is mandatory for the central office for project administration; 3 PMs is recommended for a project manager (can be a postdoc) per year.

Research Data Management

- Data – physical material or digital object; very broad definition.
- Good data management benefits researchers directly – helps with data interpretation. Ensures security – prevents data loss. Data preservation (project off-boarding) is important for publications; may lead to retractions of papers if there is no data to go back to for recalculation.
- Stakeholders also require RDM: funders, publishers (transparency), EU lawmakers.
- Explain the benefits of good data management. Requirements by funders is the biggest push for researchers.
- EU approach: data are open by default, unless there is a good reason to not open them. Danish Code of Conduct.
- **UCPH adopted a policy for RDM in 2022.** Minimum requirements. Researchers do not always read it, but it sets up the infrastructure.
- There is a need to think in a structured way to avoid legal issues later on (e.g. with regards to sending samples) and defined collaborators' expectations.
- Horizon Europe requirements:
 - 1 page in the proposal.
 - Projects – there need to be a responsible person; FAIR, DMP. POs check DMPs and at the end of the project ask what is open.
 - DMP – checklist/manual for researchers and project team. Horizon DMP is quite complicated but ensures compliance.
 - 5 pages for individual fellowships, 15 for collaborative projects. The 1st version does not need to be perfect but has to contain the main details.
- FAIR principles – apply for humans and machines. From sharing to re-use. Specific metadata standards in various fields.
- FAIR data is not the same as open data (deposited in a repository).

- FIAR:
 - Researchers can find data. Repositories – Zenodo, GitHub for code.
 - Need to fill in all fields of repositories for search engines. Persistent identifiers (DOI); cross references – article, dataset, ORCID.
 - Researchers can download, open and work with data. Formats.
 - All contextual info, explanations about how data were created. How can data be reused? Possible to pick options in Zenodo. CC-O: all rights waived; CC-BY – requires citing.
- RDM at UCPH:
 - Guidelines and templates are available on the intranet.
 - Training (mandatory PhD course; workshops 4 times a year).
 - National e-learning courses.
 - DPMOnline.

KU Leuven presentation: proposal peaks

- Contact people from a proposal stage remain the same if the project is funded.
- Issues with workload during the peak periods of proposal submissions – how to manage this, while combining with running projects? Requires constant adaptation.
- Reporting periods in projects are predictable and therefore easier to manage.

Supporting ERC proposals at Norre campus

- Research support is divided into 3 teams:
 - Pre-award for curiosity driven projects – excellent science: ERCs.
 - Pre-award for strategic projects.
 - Post-award.
- Number of applications, based on experience and expected after the reform:
 - StGs and CoGs – 15 per year each.
 - AdGs – 12 per year.
 - SyGs – 10 per year.
 - PoC – 4 per year.
 - All campuses 100-140 per year?
- General support:
 - Provision of information: funding newsletters; intranet – grant writing toolbox, tips and tricks; info meetings.

- Support for fundraising strategy, career planning; department meetings; individualized support on request (CVs, 1:1 strategy meetings).
- Application writing support: writing workshops; reading through proposals and giving feedback; pre/post-submission check (PhD certificates etc.).
- ERC supports novel research in any field, only evaluation criterion is excellence. No set structure for applications. 2-step evaluation:
 - Step 1: panel members with general expertise, only B1+CV, remote >> physical meeting for ranking (A, B, C). Top 44 that get A go to step 2.
 - Step 2: remote by panel (generalists) + experts >> panel meeting + interview with the panel >> ranking list (scores A or B).
- B1 has to capture attention. B2 – nitty gritty how everything will work. Excellence of the project and PI are assessed, but project is more important. ERC cannot be just continuation for the PI, there has to be some break(through), should not be easily predicted, even for AdGs. This is easier for StGs.
- Activities:
 - Intro meetings with PIs.
 - Planning of the application process, advice on panels.
 - Checking CVs, advice on how to tailor them.
 - Feedback on drafts.
 - Interview practice and sparring.
- CVs – not bibliometrics, but focus is on research results or other outputs (not just publications, but also impact in policy etc.).
- Online meetings on the calls – disseminate info to potential applicants: intro to the ERC/call; presentation by a panel member; presentation by a successful applicant; Q&A.
- Timeline – example of AdGs due in Aug 2025:
 - May: individual start-up meetings; set up applications in the portal; May 22 call opens.
 - June: consultations with financial advisors, talks with department heads.
 - June-August: feedback.
 - Mid-August: support letters are given once the budget is approved.
 - Submission – final check – resubmission if needed – couple of days before the deadline.
- Mock interviews:
 - Panel in Brussels use Webex – use the same for the mock interviews.
 - The presentation is delivered by a researcher as planned.
 - Ideally there are people with panel experience at the mock interview.
 - Support staff have collected the types of questions from multiple interviews.

- Does UCPH prohibit some researchers from submitting? Support staff can suggest not submitting, but ultimately the decision lies with the head of the department whether to agree to the budget.
- All researchers go through the support staff for letters, but do not have to take their advice.

ERC workshop at Helsinki University

- Currently for SSH; other disciplines are not as willing to share their proposals. Peer support.
- Grant coach reads applications and provides feedback. Grant advisors give practical and technical advice, first contact.

Supporting MSCA-PF proposals

- Last year, 130 proposals were submitted. Get around 40 proposals funded each year.
- Focus on MSCA-PF within the internationalization strategy.
- Research and training. It is likely fellows will not continue at UCPH after the end of the project. Will they stay in academia or go to business?
- Two types – European and global.
- Success rate 15-16%? At UCPH success rate is 26-29% in health and technology.
- There are issues with global fellowships. Salaries are too small to go to the US; some management money has to go to the other institutions and sometimes they want all of it, which is not acceptable to UCPH.
- European fellowships are better therefore.
- Training is a very important aspect! Impact in careers.
- Master class for people who are applying to come to UCPH – 2 days online. This is also recorded.
- When providing feedback on proposals, refer to the online materials.
- Sometimes tell supervisors that certain candidates are not good fit (e.g. not a very strong CV etc.).
- The finance department needs to be informed and the proposal needs to be added to the system.
- Support staff checks part A, but the fellow or supervisor submit.

- If the proposal is funded, support staff collect data for the portal and fill it in. Provide info to finances and HR. Transfer from pre- to post-award (amendments etc.).
- UCPH support staff contact POs if needed, not fellows.
- The Finance department does bookkeeping.
- Support staff reminds halfway about rules, including on Open Access.
- There used to be incentives for supervisors to bring in fellows (500K DDK), but not anymore. This was university money that could be used for anything. Now information to supervisors, workshop, writing guides, online support for writing, re-using PFs for other schemes.
- Issues:
 - Some departments have very few PFs.
 - Poor English of some fellows – corrected by ChatGPT now, not staff.
 - Some start very late.
 - Supervisors are not always involved – they should read at least objectives.
- Implementation issues:
 - Non-compliance with OA rules.
 - PFs do not mention EU funding.
 - Do not inform support staff about changes, unexpected changes in personal life.
 - Many rejected reports, e.g. because training is not well described.
 - Unauthorized use of training budgets by supervisors.
 - Arguments between supervisor and fellows. To address this, support staff organize a start-up meetings for funded projects; ask to write them early to solve issues.
- Start-up meetings participants: fellow, supervisor, financial controller. Discuss budget, OA rules, reporting.
- After PFs: in most cases no money to keep people. They leave UCPH or academia. PFs are made aware of this upfront, help them find other postdoc grants.
- No limit on PFs with one supervisor.

MSCA-PF support at other universities

- Focus on incoming PFs. Mentoring, face-to-face meetings, guidelines. Training needs to match supervisors' skills. Promotion by supervisors, Euraxess, CrowdHelix.
- Workshop for PFs:
 - Info session: overview, practical tips, structure of the application; Q&A + exercise explanation.

- Exercise: simplified template is provided and prospective PFs submit. Workshop – presentations, feedback, discussion.

Post-award

- Post-award team – a specialized unit to support project coordinators.
- Support started in 2002, when one person one hired to support proposals. Also, internal audit found that there were many errors in reporting which was very costly. Decided to introduce specialized support, especially for project coordinators, when UCPH signs the GA. **Post-award support is mandatory for coordinated projects.** There used to be one central EU post-award unit for this, but now support is at the 3 campuses. Support for partner projects is also at campuses.
- Coordinated projects: 7 H2020, 3 DNs and 13 RIA/IA/CSA in HE. 4 people. Support from GA to the project end:
 - **3 PMs per year for a coordinator from the support unit are mandatory to budget.** Hours are tracked and money is given back to PIs if not used.
 - 3 PMs per year for project managers are recommended.
 - For projects where UCPH is a partner – help with GA and helpdesk, but implemented more locally. Support in the future for partner projects is unclear at the moment.
- Tasks of coordinators from support unit:
 - Grant agreement preparation – help with following all the procedures. Legal also helps facilitate CA.
 - Contact point for PO/portal from the central unit. Specialization is beneficial – support staff know how to phrase requests and communicate with the PO.
 - Daily support with EU GA compliance.
 - Follow communication between the management team and beneficiaries (relationship building, content etc.).
 - Do amendments.
 - Act as a help desk for all partners.
 - Communicate rules and obligations, attend project meetings.
 - Coordinate financial reporting. Provide guidelines and a template similar to the portal (after M9), check for mistakes before submission. Know very well what is correct and what is not for actual reporting.
 - Manage consortium budget and payments at the consortium level. PI works with financial staff locally.
 - Participate in consortium meetings and reviews: present most relevant info, provide templates for reviews, good practices for advisory boards.

- Least involved in scientific reporting, this is done by PI and project manager. Templates for beneficiaries, only coordinator adds info to the portal.
- Project managers are hired by PIs, this is decentralized. Usually already employed by departments, might have scientific background, can be postdocs or active researchers. Do deliverables, scientific reporting.
- Non-project related tasks of the post-ward team:
 - Workshops and capacity building.
 - Website content on EU grant issues.
 - Help desk for EU grant management for the whole university.
- This model requires a critical mass of projects. Related questions:
 - Permanent or temporary staff?
 - Only EU post-award or other schemes too?
 - How to fund this?
- Project managers are not a requirement but strongly advised.
- Heads of departments check all budgets – overheads issue!
- Capacity building for project managers – usually new people who do not have the skills.

Audits

- 3 types of audits:
 - CFS.
 - EU audit.
 - OLAF (anti-fraud).
- The European Court of Auditors audits the EC: checks if the EC has checked beneficiaries.
- Financial Audit is possible up to 5 years after the final payment. May need to explain why you met or you traveled. Time sheets, salary slips, attendance sheets from meetings etc.
- Letter if announcement – answer immediately! Check dates.
- Team – need to have someone who can show invoices, but the auditor can also ask about procurement etc. Check all documents – there can be mistakes, but need to be able to explain them.
- Opening meeting: presentation of the organization.
- Local auditor accompanies the EU auditor.
- Closing meeting.

- Sometimes there is a long waiting time before you get a report. Ideally you want this asap to be able to make changes if needed.

IPR and business models

- Merged lighthouse (students) and technology transfer office (researchers).
- IP – need to block others from exploiting your rights. Different types:
 - Patents – tech innovations, inventions; apply to an authority.
 - Utility model – “smaller” patent.
 - Copyright – not technology; covers movies, text, drawings, design/architecture for something. Exists automatically.
 - Software can be copyrighted and commercialized; belongs to the university; other copyright to researchers.
 - Trademark – identification of a product or service (e.g. name) – use and/or registration.
 - Registered design – external appearance, requires registration, broader than copyright.
 - Trade secrets – info not known to the public, keep confidential.
 - Other rights:
 - Tangible materials – do you have the right to use this material? Material transfer agreements.
 - Plant varieties.
- Patents – for 20 years. Invention, solution to a problem, cannot patent a discovery. Requires novelty – cannot disclose the invention if you want to patent it. Also requires proving inventive step and showing industrial applicability. 18-month patents are published automatically (lens.org).
- Business models – how do you make money? Commercialization. Patent inventions, find companies that will exploit inventions against payment...
- Biotech companies often license IP from universities and take it through clinical trial phase.
- Policy (?) – do not sell IP, only license (or let it die).
- Sell/license or spin-out a company. De-risking: sell company to big pharma.
- All patent expenses are paid by the university, but sometimes this is denied. Recouped profit is split into 3 parts. University owns IP.

SSH in HE

- SSH involvement is required in other clusters beyond cluster 2, missions etc. So there is a bulk of money outside cluster 2. E.g. 2025 calls: in cluster 1, SSH is mentioned 33 times. Topics are written in a way that SSH is important.
- The best approach is integration across WPs. Projects should address all 3 types of impact (scientific, economic, societal), and SSH if needed there.
- **Sustainable development goals – include the ones you target.**
- More holistic understanding, policy-making aspects >> more effective solutions (societal resistance...).
- Barriers to SSH integration: language, cognitive constraints, integration of methods is difficult, cultural/organizational differences.
- Internal matchmaking at UCPH, facilitation by support staff. Green center.
- Annotated topic analysis – what's required, types of partners, etc.
- Societal readiness scale: TRL >> SRCS In 2025, implementation as a pilot, will probably become more common.
- TRL may be different for different components. Address SRS as TRL.
- Net4 Society resources. CrowdHelix.
- Success rates are very discouraging in cluster 2.
- Encourage SSH researchers to write 1-pagers and connect with potential STEM coordinators.
- UCPH has been successful in pillar I, but needs to improve in pillar II and get researchers to apply.

AI

- Most useful use identified to date is language editing.
- Perplexity gives resources.
- AI is not very good for writing deliverables yet.